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STATE OF INVESTMENT ACTIVITY OF UKRAINE AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES IN WAR-TIME

Abstract.

The article provides a retrospective analysis and analytical assessment of the dynamics of capital investments in agricultural enterprises during the war. The total volume of capital investments in agriculture during the war increased by 15.2% - from 70 billion UAH in 2021 to 80.6 in 2024. The annual dynamics of capital investments in agricultural enterprises decreased by 12.7% - from 49.1 billion in 2021 to 42.9 billion in 2024. The structure of sources of financing for capital investments of agricultural enterprises was assessed. A comparative analysis of the dynamics of capital investments in the economy and agriculture of Ukraine was carried out. The transformations of the regional structure of capital investments were assessed.

Keywords: *capital investments, agriculture, agricultural enterprise, sources of financing, own funds of enterprises, state support*

Introduction

The real direction of preserving the production potential of agricultural enterprises and ensuring their sustainable functioning is the development of investment mechanisms in management aimed at restoration, minimizing losses, preventing bankruptcy and gradual development. Therefore, comprehensive monitoring of existing investment mechanisms of agricultural enterprises does not lose its relevance.

O. Popova et al. devoted their research to the assessment of modern trends in investment activity in agriculture [1]. S. Tkachenko [2] focused on determining the factors of activating investment activity in the agricultural sector of the economy and outlined effective mechanisms for practical implementation.

A sufficiently thorough analysis of investment activity trends in the agricultural sector was carried out by T. Matsyhora [3]. The author focused on indicative measurement of the advantages and disadvantages of the structure of sources of financing capital investments in agriculture. I. Makalyuk et al. [4] focused their attention on a comprehensive assessment of the current state of agricultural enterprises, a comparative characteristic of the set of economic and financial indicators of activity before and during the war. As priority areas for increasing the investment attractiveness of the agricultural sector of the economy in wartime conditions, S. Kachula and E. Mogolivets [5] emphasize the need to develop and organizationally implement an effective policy of supporting agricultural investments by providing benefits, subsidies and developing grant programs for our agribusiness.

S. Bilous and S. Novotny [6] also link the need and reality of activating investment activity in the agricultural sector of the economy with state support. Comprehensive studies of the impact on the functioning of the agricultural sector of the economy and the justification of strategic directions for the post-war restoration of the industry, which are reflected in the work of O. Bulyk [7], focus on the need to activate the investment activity of agricultural enterprises and agriculture as a whole.

At the same time, comprehensive monitoring and analysis of the system of indicators of the current state of investment in agricultural enterprises requires more in-depth research and systematic assessment.

The purpose of the article is to monitor indicators of the dynamics of capital investment in agricultural enterprises in Ukraine in wartime.

Results and discussion

Over the past 15 years, the total volume of capital investments in the country's economy has increased more than 4 times - from UAH 180.6 billion in 2010 to UAH 743.0 billion in 2024. The similar growth rate in agriculture was 7.3 times (from UAH 11.1 billion in 2010 to UAH 80.6 billion in 2024).

It was established that in some periods the annual growth rates of investments in agriculture exceeded the overall indicator for the country's economy. Over the period 2022-2024, the volume of capital investments in agriculture increased by 15.2% - from UAH 70 billion in 2021 to UAH 80.6 in 2024. At the same time, the similar indicator in the economy of Ukraine as a whole increased by 10.3% - from UAH 674 to UAH 743 billion).

The share of capital investments in agriculture in the total volume gradually increased and reached its maximum in 2017 - 14.3%. Currently, this indicator is at the pre-war level of 2021 - 10.8%.

The structural analysis of the dynamics of capital investments in agricultural enterprises differentiated by their size established that the largest share of investment flows is concentrated in medium-sized enterprises - 50.3%. It should be noted that during the analyzed period, this indicator significantly exceeded 50% and even reached the mark of 58-59% (Table 1).

The share of small enterprises in terms of capital investments is almost a third (28.2%). During the war, the similar structural indicator of investment of large enterprises increased noticeably and reached its maximum during 2012-2023 - from a minimum of 5.4% in 2016 to 22.5%, recorded in 2023.

Table 1.

Retrospective dynamics of capital investments in agricultural enterprises of Ukraine, 2010-2024.

Years	Total	large enterprises		medium-sized enterprises		small enterprises		of which micro-enterprises	
		million UAH	%	million UAH	%	million UAH	%	million UAH	%
2012	19205.8	2882.5	15.0	11122.7	57.9	5200.6	27.1	1336.0	7.0
2013	18919.1	2242.3	11.9	11259.9	59.5	5417.0	28.6	1285.9	6.8
2014	18582.4	1711.8	9.2	11020.5	59.3	5850.1	31.5	1532.3	8.2
2015	29798.5	3798.3	12.7	15141.8	50.8	10858.4	36.4	2569.6	8.6
2016	50319.6	2696.4	5.4	25630.0	50.9	21993.2	43.7	6024.4	12.0
2017	64084.1	4343.3	6.8	32501.4	50.7	27239.4	42.5	6422.3	10.0
2018	66576.3	8110.1	12.2	33723.5	50.7	24742.8	37.2	6097.7	9.2
2019	59910.1	10936.0	18.3	29653.7	49.5	19320.4	32.2	3395.7	5.7
2020	50634.3	6830.6	13.5	27855.9	55.0	15947.8	31.5	717.4	1.4
2021	69966.3	10763.0	15.4	36405.0	52.0	22798.3	32.6	1715.4	2.5
2022	51355.7	9041.7	17.6	25585.3	49.8	16728.7	32.6	2747.5	5.3
2023	65150.6	14650.4	22.5	31069.3	47.7	19430.9	29.8	3493.5	5.4
2024	81764.6	17587.9	21.5	41147.3	50.3	23029.4	28.2	4207.6	5.1

Source: calculated by the authors based on statistics from the State Statistics Committee of Ukraine [8]

A comparison of the annual volumes of investment in the country's economy as a whole and in the agricultural sector proves a significant decrease in the pace of capital investment in wartime conditions. It was found that the annual volumes of capital investment in the economy as a whole remained at practically the pre-war level (the growth was 1.1% - from UAH 529 billion in 2021 to UAH 534 billion in 2024). Unlike general economic indicators, the annual volumes of capital investment in agriculture over the three years of full-scale war decreased by 12.7% - from UAH 49.1 billion in 2021 to UAH 42.9 billion in 2024. Taking into account the disappointing rates of consumer inflation and the devaluation of the national currency, the reduction in the annual dynamics of capital investment in the agricultural sector of the economy is much greater.

The share of annual capital investment in agriculture is currently 8.0%, which is 1.3% lower than the pre-war figure. A comparison of the annual growth

rates of investment in the economy and agriculture indicates the predominance of the latter in most time periods during 2010-2024.

Equity of enterprises was and remains the main source of financing for their capital investments. Over the analyzed period, the amount of own funds of agricultural enterprises directed to capital investments increased by 21.8% (or by 7.2 billion UAH). Accordingly, the share of this source of financing in the overall structure increased - from 90.6 to 93.8%. It has been established that before the full-scale invasion, the share of state financing of capital investment by farmers was a minimum of 0.2%. It is quite clear that in war conditions, the search for sources of financing for their stable functioning and minimal development falls entirely on the enterprises themselves. The lack of own funds of enterprises activates bank lending mechanisms (Table 2).

Table 2.

Dynamics of capital investment volumes in the agricultural sector by structure of financing sources, 2020-2024. UAH million

Sources of financing	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2024 in % to 2020
Total	36442.1	49127.4	32604.0	31641.9	42885.1	117.7
State budget funds	103.7	96.8	-	-	-	-
Local budgets	31.1	67.5	24.9	-	-	-
Equity of enterprises	33033.9	44627.3	30345.2	30203.0	40221.0	121.8
Bank loans and other loans	3138.9	4310.7	2224.3	1420.1	2572.3	81.9
of which loans from foreign banks	110.1	52.7	-	-	-	-
Investment companies funds	20.5	0.22	-	-	44.5	217.1
Other sources of financing	-	25.0	-	8.1	-	-

Source: calculated by the authors based on statistics from the State Statistics Committee of Ukraine [8]

The second place after the own funds of agricultural enterprises is occupied by bank lending as a source of capital investments. In conditions of martial law, the total volume of bank loans, the intended use of which was capital investments, decreased by 40% (from 4.3 to

2.6 billion UAH), and their share in the structure of financial resources decreased from 8.8% to 6.0%. Other sources of financing for investment mechanisms - funds from local budgets, investment companies and

loans from foreign banks do not exist at all or have extremely minimal volumes.

In conditions of war, a significant transformation of the regional structure of capital investments took place. Thus, according to the State Statistics Committee, as of the end of 2025, capital investment mechanisms were suspended in agricultural enterprises of the Luhansk, Donetsk and Zaporizhia regions.

Compared to the pre-war period, an increase in the regional share of capital investments was recorded in such regions as Poltava - from 6.5 to 10.6%, Vinnytsia - from 6.4 to 8.0%, Cherkasy - from 6.0 to 9.1%, Lviv - from 2.8 to 4.9%, Sumy - from 5.8 to 7.2%, Chernihiv - from 6.3 to 9.7%, Ternopil - from 4.6 to 9.1%.

Agricultural enterprises in the Odessa region reduced their share in the regional structure of capital investments - from 2.7 to 1.6%, Dnipropetrovsk region - from 5.0 to 2.4%, Mykolaiv region - from 4.6 to 2.0%, Kharkiv region - from 4.9 to 2.5%.

Conclusions. It was established that during 2022-2024, the volume of capital investments in agriculture increased by 15.2% - from 70 billion UAH in 2021 to 80.6 in 2024. The share of capital investments in agriculture remains at the pre-war level of 2021 - 10.8%. However, the annual volume of capital investments in agriculture over the three years of full-scale war decreased by 12.7% - from 49.1 billion in 2021 to 42.9 billion in 2024.

Equity of enterprises was and remains the main source of financing for their capital investments, their share in the total structure of financing sources is currently 93.8%. Insufficient provision of investment resources for small and medium-sized agribusiness and the lack of equal opportunities in access to external sources of investment financing, compared to large enterprises, exacerbate the economic inequality of organizational and legal forms in the agrarian sector of the economy and make it impossible to effectively function and further development.

The extremely complex socio-economic situation, which is only worsening as a result of the ongoing war, requires the involvement of new, adapted mechanisms for investing in the agrarian sector of the economy of our country. The need to ensure stable functioning and further gradual development requires the implementation of a set of measures that can help agrarians not only preserve their resource and production potential, but also be able to effectively function and overcome the challenges of today.

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